

H2020 - Research and Innovation Action

APPLICATE^{*}

**Advanced Prediction in Polar regions and beyond: Modelling, observing system design and Linkages associated with a Changing Arctic climaTE
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Milestone 18 Clustering Plan

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

There are a number of European and international activities that are related to some of the activities planned in APPLICATE. Effective clustering is needed in APPLICATE to facilitate coordination and exploit synergies. To ensure effective collaboration with partners from Europe, North America and the wider international community, this document contains an updated Clustering Plan that was developed together with the partners in the context of the APPLICATE project. The strategy employed here is to focus on a limited number of clustering activities that are given full attention to make a difference.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Background and motivation

Advancing polar predictive capacity in the Arctic and understanding the impact of Arctic climate change on the weather and climate in midlatitudes has attracted considerable attention in recent years. It is not surprising, thus, that there are numerous projects tackling these issues. The advantage is that there is a critical mass needed to make much needed progress. However, in order to avoid unnecessary duplication and exploit synergies, effective coordination—or clustering as it is called in this document—is needed. The clustering concept employed in the APPLICATE project is outlined in this Plan.

1.2. Organisation of the plan

The Clustering Plan is a living document that will be updated throughout the lifetime of the project. The actual Plan is described in section 2. It contains a list of partners along with envisaged activities for three classes of partners: European, North American and international. The Plan is followed by a concise summary of the risks that could possibly jeopardize effective clustering and a list of critical interdependencies. The document finishes with a list of references and a description of acronyms.

2. CLUSTERING PLAN

2.1. General activities

APPLICATE has been actively engaging in clustering. Rather than working with a large number of small individual partners, APPLICATE aims to cluster with major European and international projects and players (see Table 1 for details).

Table 1: List of major partners for which clustering activities are carried out.

Partner	Point(s) of contact
<i>European partners</i>	
PRIMAVERA	Pier Luigi Vidale, Malcolm Roberts
CRESCENDO	Colin Jones
Blue-Action	Steffen Olsen, Daniela Matei
EU-PolarNet	Nicole Biebow
ICE-ARC	Jeremy Wilkinson
INTAROS	Stein Sandven
INTERACT	Margareta Johansson
Nunataryuk	Hugues Lantuit
ARICE	Nicole Biebow, Veronica Willmott

ARCSAR	Bent-Ove Jamtli
iCUPE	Tuukka Petäjä
KEPLER	Nick Hughes
SPICES	Steffen Tietsche
European Polar Board	Renuka Badhe
S2S4E	Isadora Jimenez
Michael Kingston Associates, London, UK	Michael Kingston
International Centre for Reindeer Husbandry, Norway	Anders Oskal
AXA XL, London, UK	John Wardman

North American partners

Sea Ice Prediction Network Phase 2 (SIPN2)	Cecilia Bitz Edward Blanchard-Wrigglesworth Uma Bhatt
National Center for Atmospheric Research (NCAR)	Julio Bacmeister Gokhan Danabasoglu Clara Deser Andrew Gettelman Cecile Hannay Marika Holland David Bailey
National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA)	Mitch Bushuk Taneil Uttal Michael Winton
University of California Irvine	Yannick Peings
University of Colorado	Amy Solomon
National Snow And Ice Data Centre (NSIDC)	Peter Pulsifer
US Arctic Commission	John Farrel
Environment and Climate Change Canada (ECCC)	Barbara Casati Bertrand Denis Stephane Laroche Emmanuel Poan Pierre Pellerin

	Bill Merrifield Gregory Smith Neil Swart
University of Toronto	Paul Kushner
Université du Québec à Montréal	Arlan Dirkson
McGill University	Bruno Tremblay
University of Ottawa	Natalie Carter
Simon Fraser University	David Hik
Institute of the North	Veronica Slajer, Ian Laing
Arctic Athabaskan Council, Canada	Cindy Dickson
Treadwell Development	Mead Treadwell
<i>International partners</i>	
Year of Polar Prediction (YOPP)	Thomas Jung Jonny Day Gunilla Svensson Irina Sandu François Massonnet
Belmont projects	James Screen and Daniela Matei
MOSAiC	Markus Rex
S2S Prediction Project	Frederic Vitart
WGSIP	Doug Smith and Bill Merryfield
IASC	Thomas Spengler
APECS	Gerlis Fugmann
GEWEX GASS	Irina Sandu
Polar Research Institute of China (PRIC)	Cheng Wenfang
Korean Maritime Institute (KMI)	Justin Kim
SAON / IASC data committee	Peter Pulsifer

High-level coordination between the different activities is ensured by frequent communication between the coordination offices of the various projects,

participation/representation to each other’s annual meetings, and organisation of joint events at international conferences.

2.2. Clustering activities with European projects

Effective clustering with other European projects in particular is critical. For this reason, an EU-Polar Cluster of projects has been established that comprises the eleven projects (as of November 2019) as in Table 3.

Table 3: Projects composing the EU-Polar Cluster (as of November 2019)

Project name	Coordinator	Website
APPLICATE	Thomas Jung (Alfred Wegener Institute)	http://appliccate.eu
ARCSAR	Bent-Ove Jamtli (Joint Rescue Coordination Centre North Norway)	www.arcsar.eu
ARICE	Nicole Biebow (Alfred Wegener Institute)	www.arice.eu
Blue-Action	Steffen Olsen (Danish Meteorological Institute) Daniela Matei (Max Planck Institute for Meteorology)	http://www.blue-action.eu
EU-Polar Net	Nicole Biebow (Alfred Wegener Institute)	http://www.eu-polar.net
ICE-ARC	Jeremy Wilkinson (British Antarctic Survey)	http://www.ice-arc.eu
iCUPE	Tuukka Petäjä (Helsinki University)	https://www.atm.helsinki.fi/icupe/
INTAROS	Stein Sandven (Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center)	http://www.intaros.eu
INTERACT	Margareta Johansson (Lund University)	http://www.eu-interact.org
KEPLER	Nick Hughes (Norwegian Meteorological Institute)	https://kepler-polar.eu/
Nunataryuk	Hugues Lantuit (Alfred Wegener Institute)	http://www.nunataryuk.org
European Polar Board	Renuka Badhe	www.europeanpolarboard.org

Coordination of activities within the EU-Polar Cluster is facilitated by regular communication between the various project offices, and a common calendar of major international events to identify opportunities for organisation of joint side-events. Some recent activities carried out within the EU-Polar Cluster and other European projects as for the year 2019 are summarised in Table 4.

Table 4: Clustering activities with other EU projects (2019).

Type of activity	Title	Dates, location	Partner projects
Meeting	EU-PolarNet General Assembly 2019	26.03.2019, Lisbon (PT)	EU-PolarNet

Meeting	Joint APPLICATE-Blue Action meeting on PAMIP simulations	4.4.2019, Hamburg (DE)	Blue-Action
Presentation	European Climate Change Adaptation Conference (ECCA).	28.05.2019, Lisbon (PT)	JPI Climate and Climateurope
Meeting	EU-Polar Cluster meeting	4.06.2019	EU-Polar Cluster
Workshop	2nd EU Climate Modelling "Workshop on Climate Prediction in the Arctic-Atlantic Sector"	5-7.06.2019, Bergen (NO)	Blue-Action, PRIMAVERA, CRESCENDO, EUCP
Booth	Booth at Arctic Circle 2019	10-13.10.2019, Reykjavik (IS)	EU-Polar Cluster
Task Group	Data Management	Semi-regular meetings and telecons	EU-Polar Cluster
Task Group	Stakeholder engagement	Semi-regular meetings and telecons	EU-Polar Cluster
Task Group	Communication and outreach	Semi-regular meetings and telecons	EU-Polar Cluster
Task Group	Education and training	Semi-regular meetings and telecons	EU-Polar Cluster
Case study development	APPLICATE energy case studies	Collaboration on the case studies	S2S4E
Workshop	Improved safety and environmentally sound operations in the Arctic Ocean - how to move forward?	23.01.2019, Arctic Frontiers, Tromso, Norway	EU-Polar Cluster
Breakout session	Connecting Arctic science with society: lessons learned and progress	11.10.2019, Arctic Circle, Reykjavik, Iceland	EU-PolarNet, Nunataryuk

2.3. Clustering with North American partners—Contribution to the Transatlantic Ocean Research Alliance

APPLICATE contributes to implementing the Transatlantic Ocean Research Alliance through strong collaboration with coordinating bodies and numerous individual collaborators from the US (e.g. Sea Ice Prediction Network Phase II, NCAR) and Canada (e.g. Environment and Climate Change Canada). An overview of activities with partners in Canada and USA is given in deliverable D8.9 (October 2019).

2.4. Clustering with partners at the international level

Further clustering activities are carried out on an international level, some of which are listed in Table 5.

Table 5: Clustering at international level.

Activity	Leader	Action	Due date
5th Polar Prediction Workshop	Ed Blockley, Ruben Cruz Garcia	Participation to a workshop	7-9.05.2018
Seminar on an Arctic Index, Nord University	Halldór Jóhannsson		21.05.2018
6th China-Nordic Arctic Cooperation Symposium	Halldór Jóhannsson	Participation to a conference (Talk)	23-25.05.2018
POLAR2018	Juan Camilo Acosta, Svenya Chripko, Halldór Jóhannsson. Rym Msadek, Thomas Jung	Participation to a conference (Talk)	15-26.06.2018
Adaptation Futures 2018	Dragana Bojovic	Participation to a conference (Talk)	18-22.06.2018
The EC booth at Adaptation Futures	Dragana Bojovic	Participation in activities organised jointly with other H2020 project(s)	6.2018
Oral evidence to UK House of Commons Environment Audit Committee inquiry on 'The Changing Arctic'	Richard Wood	Participation to an event other than a conference or workshop	3.07.2018
3rd User Group meeting	User Engagement Team	Organisation of a workshop	7.2018

Article in the Polar Journal: Bojovic, D. and Terrado, M. (2018) Conference report: Insights from the APPLICATE User Group meeting, Polar Journal, doi.org/10.1080/2154896X.2018.1477426		Non-scientific and non-peer reviewed publications (popularised publications)	7.2018
EMS Annual Meeting 2018	Lauriane Batté	Participation to a conference (Talk)	05.09.2018
WCRP S2S/S2D International Conferences	Lauriane Batté	Participation to a conference (Poster)	17-21.09.2018
The EU Arctic Cluster booth at Arctic Circle 2018	Halldór Jóhannsson	Participation in activities organised jointly with other H2020 project(s)	19-21.10.2018
FAMOS Meeting	Claudia Hinrichs	Participation to a conference (Talk)	23.-26.10.2018
SAON side event seminar on observations	Halldór Jóhannsson		24.10.2018
Second Arctic Science Ministerial	Thomas Jung, Halldór Jóhannsson		25-26.10.2018
ACI 13 th Shipping summit	Halldór Jóhannsson		05-06.12.2018
AGU Fall Meeting 2018	Luisa Cristini	[Participation to a conference (POSTER)]	10-14.12.2018
Korea Arctic Week	Halldór Jóhannsson		11-14.12.2018
APPLICATE - Blue Action meeting on PAMIP simulations	Tido Semmler	Organisation of a workshop	19.12.2018
AMS Annual Meeting 2019	Thomas Jung	Participation to a conference (Poster)	6-10.01.2019
YOPP Arctic Science workshop	Claudia Hinrichs, Morten Køltzow, Gunilla Svensson	Participation to a workshop	14.-16.01.2019

Arctic Frontiers 2019 side event 'Improved safety and environmentally sound operations in the Arctic ocean - how to move forward?'	Dragana Bojovic, Marta Terrado	Organisation of a workshop	23.01.2019
APPLICATE General Assembly 2019	Project Team	Organisation of a workshop	28-30.01.2019
Early Career Scientists Workshop	Gerlis Fugmann, Andrea Schneider (both APECS)	Organisation of a workshop	30.01-01.02.2019
Video Interview Peter Bauer		Video/film	18.02.2019
ECRA General Assembly	Thomas Jung	Participation to a conference (Talk)	27-28.02.2019
EU-PolarNet General Assembly 2019	Thomas Jung	Participation to a conference (Talk)	13.03.2019
European Polar Board	Halldór Jóhannsson		27-28.03.2019
ARICE general assembly	Halldór Jóhannsson		29.03.2019
APPLICATE - Blue Action meeting on PAMIP simulations	Tido Semmler	Organisation of a workshop	04.04.2019
EGU General Assembly 2019	Luisa Cristini, Daniela Flocco, Sally Woodhouse, Svenya Chripko, Linus Magnusson, Gabriele Arduini, Irina Sandu, Jonathan Day	Participation to a conference (Talk)	08-12.04.2019
China-Nordic Arctic Research Forum	Halldór Jóhannsson		07-09.05.2019
Arctic Circle China Forum	Halldór Jóhannsson		10-11.05.2019

15th AMS Conference on Polar Meteorology and Oceanography	Gunilla Svensson, Thomas Jung	Participation to a conference (Talk)	19-23.05.2019
Arctic Science Summit Week 2019	Pablo Ortega	Participation to a conference (remote Talk)	24.05.2019
21st WGSIP session	Doug Smith, Lauriane Batté	Participation to a workshop	29-31.05.2019
CMIP6 workshop for the French modeling groups	Rym Msadek, Thomas Oudar, Emilia Sanchez	Participation to a conference (Talk)	27-28.05.2019
European Climate Change Adaptation Conference (ECCA). Presentation at the joint booth of JPI Climate and Climateurope	Dragana Bojovic, Marta Terrado	Participation in activities organised jointly with other H2020 project(s)	28.05.2019
Sea ice in the Earth System: a multidisciplinary perspective	Rym Msadek	Organisation of a workshop	04-06.062019
Sea ice in the Earth System: a multidisciplinary perspective	Rym Msadek, Svenya Chripko	Participation to a conference (Talk)	04-06.06.2019
EU-Polar Cluster meeting	Luisa Cristini, Marta Terrado, Gerlis Fugmann, Halldor Johannsson	Participation in activities organised jointly with other H2020 project(s)	04.06.2019
2nd EU Climate Modelling "Workshop on Climate Prediction in the Arctic-Atlantic Sector"	Thomas Jung	Participation to a workshop	05-07.06.2019
APPLICATE Energy Case Study	Dragana Bojovic, Marta Terrado, Isadora Christel, Juan Acosta, Pablo Ortega, Markus Donat, Llorenç Lledó, Halldór	Non-scientific and non-peer reviewed publications (popularised publications); website	13.06.2019

	Jóhannsson, Thomas Jung		
PAMIP Workshop 2019	Tido Semmler, Doug Smith, Lise Seland Graff	Participation to a workshop	24-27.06.2019
PAMIP Workshop 2019	Tido Semmler	Participation to a conference (Talk)	25.06.2019
Climateurope webinar: 'Climate services for energy: sharing knowledge through case studies'	Dragana Bojovic, Marta Terrado	Participation in activities organised jointly with other H2020 project(s)	27.06.2019
IGS Sea ice symposium 2019 - Presentation of APPLICATE workpackage 1	Ed Blockley	Participation to a conference (Talk)	18-23.08.2019
International Mountain Meteorology Conference	Irina Sandu	Participation to a conference (Talk)	08-13.09.2019
European Meteorological Society (EMS) Annual Meeting 2019	Thomas Jung, Jonny Day, Linus Magnusson	Participation to a conference (Talk)	09-13.09.2019
APPLICATE online course "Advancing Predictive Capability of Northern Hemisphere Weather and Climate"	Gerlis Fugmann, Andrea Schneider (both APECS)	Training	19.9.-05.12.2019
SIPN2 webinar: 'Overview of APPLICATE and its seasonal climate prediction activities'	Pablo Ortega	Participation to a conference (Talk)	17.09.2019
UK Sea Ice Group Meeting	Anne Keen	Participation to a conference (TALK)	19-20.09.2019
Northern Forum Youth Environmental school	Halldór Jóhannsson		09.10.2019
Northern Forum Breakout session - Responsible regional development	Halldór Jóhannsson		10.10.2019

The EU Arctic Cluster booth at Arctic Circle 2019	Dragana Bojovic, Marta Terrado, Halldór Jóhannsson, Gerlis Fugmann	Participation in activities organised jointly with other H2020 project(s)	10-13.10.2019
Breakout session 'Connecting Arctic science with society: lessons learned and progress'	Dragana Bojovic, Marta Terrado	Organisation of a workshop	11.10.2019
APPLICATE promotional video	BSC	Video/film	
European Polar Board	Halldór Jóhannsson		22-23.10.2019
Met Office	Heather Lawrence	Participation to an event other than a conference or workshop	28.10.19
International TOVS study conference (ITSC) 22	Heather Lawrence	Participation to a conference (Talk)	31.10.19 - 6.11.19
Regular updates on YOPP at APPLICATE meetings and vice versa	Thomas Jung Luisa Cristini	Updates on YOPP will be part of all agendas, identify possible synergies in the different areas relevant to both initiatives	Ongoing
Engage with relevant projects resulting from Belmont Forum call on climate predictability and inter-regional linkages	Thomas Jung Doug Smith	Collaboration in the context of the Polar Amplification MIP	Ongoing
Development of Single Column Model (SCM) intercomparison studies together with GEWEX GASS	Gunilla Svensson	Workshop in Stockholm to discuss new SCM studies based on the results from GASS projects GABLS4 and Larcform1.	Nov 2017
YOPPsiteMIP: Multi model evaluation of forecasts at polar supersites during YOPP	Gunilla Svensson Jonny Day	A planning workshop was held at U. Stockholm in September 2019 and a multi-model intercomparison is underway. Aiming to submit a paper to BAMS in 2020.	Ongoing
Regular updates on MOSAiC at APPLICATE	Thomas Jung Gunilla Svensson	Updates on MOSAiC will be part of all agendas, identify possible	Ongoing

meetings and vice versa		synergies in the different areas relevant to both initiatives	
YOPP Arctic Science workshop	Thomas Jung	Science workshop in preparation of the YOPP Consolidation Phase	14.-16.01.2019
PAMIP Community	Doug Smith	To coordinate PAMIP experiments and timeline (e.g., through workshops)	24-27.06.2019
SIMIP Community	Ed Blockley	Leadership of a coordinated analysis and inter-comparison of the Arctic sea ice mass budget in CMIP6 climate simulations	Ongoing
Science session at EGU2020	Luisa Cristini Jonny Day	JOint APPLICATE-YOPP science session	3-8 May 2020
Updates on APPLICATE at WGSIP meetings	Doug Smith Lauriane Batté	Inform subseasonal to interdecadal prediction community and identify possible synergies	Ongoing
User Group meetings	Dragana Bojovic Marta Terrado	Online communication and interaction during APPLICATE GA 2018 and at the Arctic Circle in 2017 and 2019	Ongoing
Coordination of observing system experiments	Irina Sandu	regular telecons with ECCC, DWD, MetNo and FMI to exchange results and plan numerical experimentation and publications	Ongoing

3. RISKS AND INTERDEPENDENCIES

3.1. Risks

The wide network of APPLICATE partners and team member involved in clustering activities ensures a variety of opportunities for collaborations with other projects and initiatives throughout the project lifetime.

Table 7: Risks to the clustering plan

Risk	Probability	Proposed risk mitigation strategy	Responsibility
Related European and international projects/activities are	Low	APPLICATE will take a proactive approach offering to organize, co-lead and synthesize clustering	Thomas Jung and Luisa Cristini

reluctant to engage in the clustering process		activities. Make use of existing links with any APPLICATE partner	
Action leaders become unavailable	Low	The clustering plan will be updated regularly and action leader confirmed. Representation of APPLICATE at key events will be decided by the Executive Board before each event.	Thomas Jung and Jonny Day

4. IMPLEMENTATION OF THE PLAN

The Clustering Plan will be implemented by the project partners and more specifically by the action leaders defined above. Clustering activities with other EU projects (e.g., EU-Arctic Cluster) will be led by the Coordinator and the Project Manager. The WP8 leaders will be ultimately responsible for ensuring APPLICATE collaboration with other international programmes and for the coordination and monitoring of the planned actions. The WP8 leaders will report to the project Executive Board on the implementation of the plan and more generally on clustering activities.

5. ACRONYMS

APECS	Association of Polar Early Career Scientists
ARCSAR	Arctic and North Atlantic Security and Emergency Preparedness Network
ARICE	Arctic Research Icebreaker Consortium
CRESCENDO	Coordinated Research in Earth System and Climate: Experiments, Knowledge, Dissemination and Outreach
ECCC	Environment and Climate Change Canada
EGU	European Geosciences Union
GEWEX	The Global Energy and Water Exchanges project, Global Atmospheric
GASS	System Studies
ICE-ARC	Ice, Climate, Economics: Arctic Research on Change
iCUPE	Integrative and Comprehensive Understanding on Polar Environments
INTAROS	Integrated Arctic Observation System
INTERACT	International Network for Terrestrial Research and Monitoring in the Arctic

KEPLER	Key Environmental monitoring for Polar Latitudes and European Readiness
MOSAiC	Multidisciplinary drifting Observatory for the Study of Arctic Climate
NCAR	National Center for Atmospheric Research
NOAA	National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration
NSIDC	National Snow And Ice Data Centre
PAMIP	Polar Amplification Model Intercomparison Project
PRIMAVERA	Process-based climate simulations: advances in high-resolution modelling and European climate risk assessment
S2S	Sub-seasonal to Seasonal
S2S4E	Sub-seasonal to Seasonal Climate Forecasting for Energy
SIMIP	Sea Ice Model Intercomparison Project
SIPN	Sea Ice Prediction Network
SPICES	Space-borne observations for detecting and forecasting sea ice cover extremes
YOPP	Year of Polar Prediction
YOPPsiteMIP	YOPP supersite model intercomparison project